

Social Participation among Asthmatic and Non-asthmatic Adolescents in Sikkim

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The main objective of the current research was to examine the level of social participation amongst asthmatic and non-asthmatic adolescents in the state of Sikkim, which includes both male and female individuals. For this purpose, the research employs purposive sampling technique. In this regard, it is worth mentioning that the study applied the participation (P scale) to examine the level of adolescent engagement in socially meaningful activities in society. An independent t-test was conducted to examine the difference in the level of participation amongst asthmatic and non-asthmatic individuals, and it was observed that a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.01$) was found between asthmatic and non-asthmatic individuals with a substantial effect size of 1.57. These findings highlight the restrictions in social participation placed on adolescents with asthma and how well they are integrated in their community which also serves as an important indicator of their overall quality of life.

Keywords: Social participation, asthma, adolescents, participation scale

In the present day, there is a high prevalence of chronic diseases like asthma, which affect a large number of people worldwide. Asthma is a noncommunicable chronic disease that is characterised by inflammation and airflow limitation resulting in episodic respiratory symptoms that can be experienced by people of all ages (WHO, 2023). It is estimated that there are approximately 334 million people suffering from asthma worldwide (Enilari & Sinha, 2019)

Although asthma is considered a physical illness that affects the respiratory system of humans, a recent study shows that people suffering from asthma are more likely to face mental health issues like anxiety and depression. Their effects are not limited to health degradation but rather suggest a major impact on their mental health as well (Greenlee et al., 2019). Furthermore, asthma has a significant impact on the physical and mental health of individuals, as well as their work and social activities. The symptoms of asthma can be experienced differently by people, as they can be characterised by coughing, wheezing, tightness in the chest, and breathlessness (Jindal et al., 2012)

In addition, inadequate management of childhood asthma can cause chronic asthma, which involves recurrent symptoms related to breathing problems. A study showed that children with asthma were 18 times more susceptible to experiencing mental health problems, and at a risk of over 14 times higher when it comes to experiencing developmental problems (Arif et al., 2015). Child asthma can cause a negative impact on attendance at school, worsen their engagement at work level and impair quality of life (Deka et al., 2022).

According to the World Health Organisation, adolescence represents a phase of rapid and often uneven development in

physical, psychological, cognitive, and emotional domains (Sanders, 2013). Adolescence is a transitional phase of human development that connects childhood and adulthood. It is interesting to note that the prevalence, incidence, and hospitalisation rates for those suffering from asthma at this phase are higher among males before puberty, as opposed to females of the same age (Fuhlbrigge et al., 2002)

As per findings from the Indian study, asthma is present in 17.23 million individuals aged 15 and above, with a prevalence rate of 2.04% (Agarwal et al., 2012). However, little is known about the social lives of asthmatic adolescents. Among teenagers, 13.1% had bronchial asthma, and within this group, 10.3% reported experiencing asthma attacks in the preceding year (Bhalla et al., 2018). Much research needs to be done in order to investigate the relationship between persons with asthma and how their social lives are affected by it.

Social participation can be defined as how individuals engage with others and take an active part in everyday social and community life (Ramond et al., 2010, p. 2148). It includes interactions with peers and families, as well as involvement in social and communal activities, which may foster a sense of belonging. Beyond the personal interactions, participation also reflects the ability to fulfil social roles and responsibilities. However, this opportunity for social engagement is not fairly distributed to all adolescents. In the course of human history, the idea of stigma and its implications have been an ever-present factor. Certain sections of the population have had limitations placed on the potential to engage in various aspects of life due to factors such as disabilities, diseases, physical abnormalities, caste, religion, race, gender, and so forth.

Consequently, the significance of participation evaluation is of paramount importance in establishing the requirements. It would include communication, mobility, self-care, domestic affairs, social relationships, community, involvement, and civic engagement (Brakel et al., 2009).

Young individuals with challenges related to asthma may face certain restrictions to be fully integrated into society. This may eventually affect their well-being and quality of life. For instance, behaviours like excessive television viewing, increased mental

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I have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

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stress, reduced physical activity, and decreased weekly travel distance may serve as contributing factors to the presence of asthma among the Indian population. Such lifestyle changes may have a bearing on the presence of asthma among the Indian population (Poongadan et al., 2015). Upon pursuing the above research papers, it is evident that the vast majority of the research has mainly concentrated on the role of physical activities and interaction with peers.

The present study research paper aims to study the differences between asthma and social participation of asthmatic and non-asthmatic adolescents aged 15-19 years residing in the North-eastern state of Sikkim and to compare the two groups for the same.

Previous studies conducted on asthma in India have reported a wide range of prevalence rates, spanning from 2% to 23% (Pal et al., 2009). While extensive research efforts are underway in various regions of India, there has been a notable dearth of research conducted in the economically disadvantaged northeastern part of the country (Deka et al., 2022).

India ranks quite poorly when compared to other developed countries, and of all its states, the north-eastern states (NE states) have so far performed very poorly according to multiple metrics that determine the health goal to be attained (Sarma et al., 2023).

Earlier studies highlight that many psychological factors such as self-esteem, peer rejection and stress have a significant hindrance to disease management. Studies by Mancuso et al. (2006), Shaikh et al. (2020), and Bruzzese et al. (2009) reveal that depression, social exclusion and social support act as barriers leading to increased isolation among adolescents with asthma. Environmental factors like high altitude and pollution seem to be a major contributor in terms of disease control (Zaeh et al., 2022). Alongside, the health system and socioeconomic factors also emerge as determinants. Con et al. (2017) and Creese et al. (2021) reveal disparities in asthma control and maternal education.

Lifestyle practices like sleep patterns, early use of substances, obesity, and longer TV viewing time were considered as contributing factors towards increasing cases of asthma (Poongaden et al., 2015). Longitudinal aspects of the studies undertaken by Jonsson et al. (2017) and Hannah et al. (2022) revealed how adolescents cope with life and strive for normalcy while living with the symptoms of the diseases, they need peer acceptance and become independent, regardless of the disease (Turk et al., 2007; & Shaikh & Kazmi, 2020) They often seek peer acceptance and desire independence irrespective of their health. Turyk et al. (2007) and Shaikh and Kazmi (2020) emphasize that stress and emotional resilience influence quality of life.

Despite the prevalence of asthma in adolescents and its negative impact on social lives/peer relationships/ academic performance and so on, there is limited research on social participation. A need for further research can be seen, which would primarily focus on the social and emotional effects of asthma on adolescents rather than the medical aspects of asthma, such as diagnosis and treatment. There is, however, a significant knowledge gap with regard to how asthma impacts social aspects, such as challenges with participation in social events including those with restrictions in engaging with friends, which would adversely affect their peer relationships or even carrying out basic daily activities at an individual level. Most research has emphasised and worked extensively with childhood asthma, thus neglecting the effect of adolescent asthma.

Research needs to be done, especially in the case of third-world

countries such as India, where chronic illnesses like asthma are often overlooked. Assessing the relationship between asthma severity and social participation in adolescents would render great value and importance to uncover more forms of treatment and future intervention that can be integrated by the community to help adolescents with asthma.

The current study employs a quasi-experimental research design, which emulates real-world scenarios, which will enable researchers to explore social involvement among adolescents with pre-existing conditions, such as asthma. The purpose of the current paper is to examine the differences in social participation among adolescents with and without asthma.

The objective of the present paper is to fill in the gaps and delve deeper than just the physical aspects of the disease and to study asthma in adolescents, which still seems to be undermined and a dearth of research can be seen, especially in the Northeastern region of India. The main objective of the research is to investigate the relationship between the presence of asthma and the participation restriction of adolescence in learning, utilising knowledge, taking care of themselves, peer relationships and overall quality of life. Through the research, the health of young adolescents with challenges related to asthma may be improved, leading to deepening of the understanding of how their overall quality of life is impacted.

Aim and Objective of the Study

The main aim of the current study is to compare and analyse the level of participation restriction among adolescents with and without asthma.

Hypothesis of the Study

H1: There is a significant difference in social participation among adolescents with and without asthma.

Method

Participants

A total of 126 research participants were recruited for the study. The participants were further divided into two equal groups consisting of 63 participants each. Both male and female participants were included in the study from Gangtok, Sikkim. Recruitment was done through schools, personal contacts and hospital administrations.

Inclusion Criteria

Age Range: Participants aged between 15 to 19 years were eligible to participate in the study.

Language Proficiency: Potential participants needed to be proficient in English. This criteria ensured effective communication during data collection

Gender: Both male and female participants were included in the study.

Medical Diagnosis: To be included in the study, participants should have been diagnosed with asthma within the last five years. The time range ensures that the condition remains relevant to their current experiences

Exclusion Criteria

Mental Health Conditions: Individuals with known mental health conditions were excluded from the study. This criteria aimed to minimise the potential impact of their capacity to deliver reliable information

Other Medical or Physical Conditions: Participants with any existing psychological, physical and medical conditions apart from asthma were excluded from the study.

The purposive sampling technique was employed to ensure that individuals met the criteria aligned with the research objectives. The procedure of selecting participants was as follows for non-asthmatic groups, potential participants were primarily identified from local schools and personal contacts. These groups of participants had no history of asthma or any other chronic, physical or mental health condition. Similarly, for the asthmatic group, participants were identified mainly from local schools, paediatric departments, healthcare centres and personal contact. These participants were diagnosed with asthma and were aged 15 to 19 years. For both groups, a screening process was done to ensure that all participants met the inclusion criteria. Before participating in the study, consent was sought from the participants, guardian and the administrative head of the school or the hospital. The consent form outlines the purpose, procedure, risks, and benefits of the research while also emphasising the voluntary nature of participation and the right to withdraw from the study at any point. Data collection was carried out through questionnaires. Moreover, the use of multiple sources for selecting the participants improves the representation of this group.

Research Design

This study employed a quasi-experimental design allowing for comparison of social participation levels among adolescents aged 15 to 19 years. The hypothesis of this study states that there is a significant difference in social participation among asthmatic and non-asthmatic adolescents. H1: there is a significant difference in social participation among asthmatic and non-asthmatic adolescents.

Measures

To assess the social participation, the Participation Scale, P scale was employed, a validated tool that was developed by an international team led by Van Brakel. Social participation can be defined as how individuals interact with other people and how actively they take part in their social and community life.

It includes interactions with peers and families, as well as involvement in social and communal activities which may foster a sense of belonging. Beyond the personal interactions, participation also reflects the ability to fulfil social roles and responsibilities. This scale consists of 18 closed, structured questions that cover these various areas such as socially engaging, communicating, their mobility, how they take care of themselves and their family and personal interactions in the community. The scale consists of 18 questions, with a maximum score of 5 for each. Therefore, a score of 0 for full participation and 90 for total restriction would be expected. The Participation Scale consists of five gradients representing various levels of restriction in social participation. In this study, the interpretation of these gradients has been taken with the assumption that "more restriction would indicate less social participation".

The validity, reliability, stability and responsiveness to change of the scale scores have been thoroughly checked in six major languages and in three countries. The Cronbach alpha value for the 18 question scale is 0.92, indicating high internal consistency (Anderson et al., 2004).

The levels of restriction in the scale are as follows: No significant restriction - 0-12; Mild restriction- 13-22; Moderate restriction- 23-32; Severe restriction- 33-52; Extreme restriction- 53-90

Variables

Asthmatic Status. This is the independent variable, which serves to investigate how asthma diagnosis impacts the social participation of adolescents, facilitating comparisons between the two groups to discern potential disparities and contributing to overall understanding of the challenges and experiences of these individuals in their social lives, with implications for targeted support and interventions.

Social Participation Levels. This is the dependent variable, which represents the outcome being measured in the study. Social participation is defined as how an individual integrates themselves and actively participates in their social and community life. This scale aims to cover various domains to study participation restrictions in persons affected by disability or other stigmatised conditions. The domains covered are mostly mobility, self-care, domestic life, interpersonal interactions, community communication, and the ability to learn and apply knowledge, skills and problem-solving. This also includes their interaction with peers as well as involvement with social and communal group activities and promotes feelings of belongingness (Ramond et al., 2010, p. 2148).

Procedure

Data collection was conducted in a private and comfortable setting to ensure confidentiality. Informed consent was taken from the guardian. The instructions were explained and 15-20 minutes were given to read and respond to the Participation scale (p scale). The responses of the scale were moved to the 'Score' column, where they are totaled and then marked to enter the total score in the "Total" box.

Data Analysis

The data collected was tested for normality of distribution using the Shapiro Wilk test and Levene's test for homogeneity of variance. However, since the data was normally distributed and independent, a t-test was conducted to compare the means of the groups. Statistical significance was determined with a p value less than 0.05 suggesting a significant difference exists in participation level between the two groups.

Ethics

In the research study, informed consent was carefully elicited from the guardians of the participating adolescents, who were fully informed of the purpose of the study and the procedure. The participants were made aware of the voluntary nature of the study and the right to withdraw at any time. Overall, the study aimed at furthering the knowledge concerning the impact of asthma, which may be associated with increased support and interventions. Data security measures were used to guard the collection of information, where hard copies were stored safely and soft copies were encrypted on an external drive, which was accessible only to the authorised personnel and the research supervisor. The study was carried out in accordance with the guideline of the Institutional Review Board and anonymity of the participants in any publication or presentation, making the ethical standards meeting the ethical standards in conducting the study.

Results and Discussion

This chapter delves into the data analysis, results, and discussion of social participation among Asthmatic and non-asthmatic adolescents.

Table 1(a)*Shows the Gender Distribution of the Participants*

Gender	Male	Female
Asthmatic	21	42
Non-asthmatic	31	32

The socio-demographic data reveal that among the asthmatic adolescents, there were 21 male participants and 42 female participants (66.67% of asthmatics), while among the non-asthmatic adolescents, there were 31 male participants (49.2%) and 32 female participants (50.8%). Overall, 58.7% were females, while 41.3% were male participants.

Table 1(b)*Shows the Age Distribution of the Participants in Both Groups*

Age (in years)	15 yrs	16 yrs	17 yrs	18 yrs	19 yrs	Total
Asthmatic	15	13	23	8	4	63
Non asthmatic	8	13	22	15	5	63
Total	23	26	45	23	9	126
% of total	18.25%	20.6%	35.7%	18.2%	7.14%	100%

Table 1(c)*Shows the Grades of Participation Restrictions among Different Age Groups in Both Asthmatic and Non-asthmatic Adolescents*

Asthmatic	15 yrs	16 yrs	17 yrs	18 yrs	19 yrs
Nil	1	1	1	1	2
Mild	6	6	7	2	1
Moderate	4	4	9	5	1
Severe	4	1	6	0	0
Extreme	0	1	0	0	0
Non-asthmatic	15 yrs	16 yrs	17 yrs	18 yrs	19 yrs
Nil	2	2	5	7	2
Mild	6	11	17	8	3

Table 2*Descriptive Statistics for the same*

Groups	N	Mean	Std. error mean	Standard Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
Asthmatic Adolescents	63	22.9048	1.31355	10.4225	0.684	1.467
Non-Asthmatic Adolescents	63	10.4921	0.51395	4.07935	0.234	-0.799

The mean scores of asthmatic adolescents on social restriction were $M = 22.9048$, ($SD = 10.4225$), while the score of non-asthmatic adolescents on social restriction was $M = 10.4921$, ($SD = 4.07935$). The average score of social restriction was higher in asthmatic adolescents compared to non-asthmatic adolescents, which indicates that social participation is higher for non-asthmatic adolescents. Individual differences were greater in asthmatic adolescents than in non-asthmatic as reported by the standard deviation. The data of the asthmatic group was slightly skewed and not kurtotic, while that data of the non-asthmatic group had no skewness and kurtosis.

Table 3*Showing the Normality Test for the Data*

Shapiro-wilk test			
Variables	Statistics	df	Sig.
Asthmatic	0.964	63	0.066
Non asthmatic	0.967	63	0.085

Note. A low p-value suggests a violation of the assumption of normality

Table 3 shows the tests of normality for both groups of adolescents using Shapiro-Wilk's test. The results were found to be $W (df = 63) = 0.964$, $p = 0.066$ for Asthmatic group, and $W (df = 63) = 0.967$, $p = 0.085$. The data collected was normally distributed. The histograms showed that the population is approximately normally distributed, and the Shapiro Wilk Test of Normality has quantitative evidence of data being normally distributed. The Q-Q plot showed that the data are slightly skewed for both groups.

Table 4*Independent Sample t-test*

Social Restriction	t	df	sig.	d
	8.800	80.549	0.000	1.57

Note. $H_a \mu_{asthmatic} \neq \mu_{non-asthmatic}$

$H1$: There is a significant difference in the social participation of asthmatic and non-asthmatic adolescents.

In order to test social participation, an independent sample t-test was done. Since the test violated the test for homogeneity, the equal

variances are not assumed. Table 4 shows the result of the independent sample t-test. The test was found to be significant, $t(126) = 8.800, p < .01; d = 1.57$. Thus, the alternative hypothesis is retained. The effect size was found to be, $d = 1.57$ indicating a substantially large difference.

These results indicated a significant difference in the social participation of the asthmatic and non-asthmatic adolescents.

Discussion

The present study aimed to compare the levels of social participation among adolescents with and without asthma. This section of the paper comprehensively explores the implications and the insights derived from the findings. The findings are in alignment with the existing literature. The result of the research strongly supports the initial hypothesis that revealed a big difference in the level of social participation of an adolescent with and without asthma.

The independent t-test conducted produced a significant result ($p < 0.01$) with a notably substantial effect size of 1.57, indicating a large difference between the two groups.

This can be understood by taking precedence of Cohen's (1988) convention to interpret effect size in psychological research.

Moreover, the scale used in this study covered various areas of social engagement, communication, mobility, self-care, domestic life, interpersonal interactions, major life areas, and community, social, and civic participation. Therefore, in the light of social participation, various facets were covered.

In this study of adolescent participants from age 15 to 19, the number of participants aged 17 years old represented 35.7% of the sample. Interestingly, there was a higher incidence of females in gender distribution among the asthmatic adolescent participants with 66.67% being female and 33% being male.

It's worth mentioning that this study was in agreement with research conducted by Fuhlbrigge et al. (2002) which showed a prevalence of asthma among females. The earlier research indicated that before puberty, asthma rates were initially higher in males compared to females of the same age in terms of occurrence, frequency and hospitalization rates. During the period of adolescence, a shift was observable in which asthma remained more prevalent in women compared to men. These findings create a connection to the present study and research that emphasises how asthma evolves and patterns change with presence in females than males.

The present study aimed at assessing the degree to which teenagers between the ages of 15 and 19 with and without asthma face restrictions in their participation. Findings of the study revealed that those without asthma showcased no significant restrictions to mild participation restrictions. On the other hand, an adolescent with asthma experienced varying degrees of limitation, ranging from moderate to severe, hindering their participation. All of these findings are consistent with the study conducted by Gazzotti et al. (2013) in Brazil, which explores asthma control and its influence on the day-to-day life of the patient. The study revealed that people suffering from uncontrollable asthma reported a more negative impact on their daily life, sleep, social interaction, and regular physical activity compared to those with controlled or somewhat controlled asthma. This correspondence between the presentation of the study findings and the previous research also underscores the importance of multifaceted aspects of asthma on daily lives and the

involvement of adolescence.

Johnson et al. (2017) investigated asthma among adolescents and reported a high frequency of symptoms, especially during physical activity, which remained a challenge for engagement. Most children with asthma may have less reactive lives and engagement in activities. Another study, such as Poongadan et al. (2015) in India, investigated the relationship between lifestyle factors. The study emphasizes how asthma can affect daily routines and behavioural habits of an individual.

While this present study was not focused on these specific lifestyle factors, it contributes to the broader understanding of the complex interplay between asthma and daily life across areas of communication and participation both personally and socially too. Further research taking each of these areas as individual variables can be undertaken to explore the far-reaching effects of chronic illnesses like asthma on the fragile lives of adolescents.

While previous literature has explored the impact of asthma on old people and children and the various aspects of their lives very little research has been done on one of the most crucial transitional phases of an individual's life, that is adolescence. Furthermore, little to no research exists for regions like North-East India.

During the literature review of this study the author found almost no studies relating to asthma for their home state, Sikkim. Hence, this study may serve as a starting point in this uncharted territory.

From studies like these, time and again it is understood that there exists a difference in people's lives suffering chronic conditions like asthma from those who do not. This highlights the need for extensive research to find and study the causes and extent to which these conditions impose limitations in their lives. It is essential to emphasize that adolescents with asthma can lead fulfilling social lives with the right support.

Future research could explore more nuanced factors influencing social participation among asthmatic adolescents. In addition to this, it would have been beneficial to have a larger and more representative sample size, encompassing a broader demographic range.

Conclusion

The current study shows a large difference in the levels of participation, thereby supporting the hypothesis of the study. The findings highlight the need to deal with the disparities or the restrictions posed on those with asthma especially during such transitional phase of their lives. The presence of an extensive list of parameters included in the research tool has ensured a holistic understanding of restrictions and how it affect the lives of adolescents with asthma compared to those without. This section of the paper effectively shows a holistic approach towards the effect of asthma on social participation and casts a spotlight on the disease's influence on integration in the community.

Implications of the Study

Psychosocial Support Programs- Targeted psychological support programmes to assist youth with asthma, coping with emotional and social difficulties associated with the condition.

Research and Academia- The study could stimulate further research in related fields in order to gain a deeper understanding of the impacts of chronic health conditions during a transitional phase.

Policy and Advocacy- The findings may strengthen policy implication and may guide policy makers in creating legislations that support the rights and needs of those with asthma

Community Awareness- The research aims at creating awareness within the community about the importance of inclusivity and rehabilitation to provide the support that is needed for people with asthma. The parents and guardians can also gain insights into the needs and concerns of their children and hence lead to more effective support and communication.

Limitations and Recommendations

The study has a few limitations such as the sample size which may restrict its generalisability. The findings of the current study may remain limited to the region of Sikkim. The study could also be improved by determining the degree of asthma, severity and exploring the appropriate level of participation restriction. It could also be advantageous to explore sequential explanatory methodology for determining the essential causes of these restrictions.

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Received February 9, 2026

Revision received March 8, 2026

Accepted March 10, 2026